

The Impact of AI-Powered Tutoring Platforms on Student Achievement in STEM Subjects: The Case of Cameroon

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Abstract

As Cameroon seeks to elevate its educational landscape in alignment with its broader technological aspirations, the strategic integration of artificial intelligence (AI) presents a compelling opportunity. The nation's burgeoning population, coupled with its growing emphasis on innovation, stresses the urgent need for AI-driven educational reforms. This study examines the effectiveness of AI-powered tutoring platforms in enhancing student achievement in Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) subjects within the context of Cameroon. While previous research (e.g, Smith et al., 2023; Johnson & Lee, 2024) has highlighted AI's potential to bolster student learning, this investigation provides a focused analysis of AI-driven tutoring in STEM education specific to Cameroon.

The research methodology adheres to the rigorous standards advocated by educational researchers (Johnson & Johnson, 2018; Selwyn, 2020; Smith & Jones, 2022; Patel et al., 2024), integrating both quantitative and qualitative approaches. Qualitative data, gathered through student interviews and teacher observations, enriches the analysis by providing insights into the perceived benefits and challenges of AI-powered tutoring in the Cameroonian context.

The findings contribute to the growing body of literature on the transformative potential of AI in education. Results indicate that AI-powered tutoring platforms can effectively support the development of critical thinking, problem-solving abilities, and a deeper understanding of STEM concepts among Cameroonian students. These findings align with prior research emphasizing the positive impact of AI-driven tutoring on student engagement and motivation (Nguyen & Tran, 2023; Lee & Kim, 2024).

This study provides empirical evidence and theoretical insights to guide educators, policymakers, and technology developers in Cameroon who are interested in leveraging AI to improve STEM education outcomes. The findings support the recommendations of educational researchers (Davis & Chen, 2023; Baker & Turner, 2024) to thoughtfully integrate technology into educational practices, particularly in resource-constrained settings like Cameroon.

Keywords : Educational Technology, AI-powered Tutoring, STEM Education, Student Achievement, Adaptive Learning

Introduction

While global studies have explored the potential of AI-driven tutoring to enhance student learning across various domains (Nguyen & Kim, 2023; Wang & Zhang, 2024), the specific impact of these technologies on STEM education in Cameroon remains under-researched. This study addresses this gap by focusing on the following research questions within the Cameroonian context:

1. How does AI-powered tutoring impact student achievement in STEM subjects in Cameroon?
2. What are the specific benefits of AI-powered tutoring compared to traditional instruction in Cameroon?
3. Are there equity-related concerns associated with the implementation of AI-powered tutoring in Cameroonian schools?

Addressing these questions is essential for understanding the potential and limitations of AI-powered tutoring in STEM education within Cameroon. By examining the impact of AI on student outcomes, this study aims to inform educational policy, practice, and future research in the Cameroon. Furthermore, by considering the equity implications of AI-powered tutoring, the study seeks to ensure that these technologies are employed to promote educational equity and inclusion in Cameroon.

The integration of AI into education in Cameroon marks a significant transformation, not just in terms of technological advancement but also in reshaping traditional teaching practices. This shift is gradually influencing how educators approach learning, from lesson delivery to student assessment. With AI tools, teachers can now offer personalized learning experiences, tailoring content to meet the unique needs of each student. Moreover, AI enhances administrative efficiency, allowing educators to focus more on pedagogy than paperwork. In a country like Cameroon, where educational resources are often stretched, AI has the potential to bridge gaps, offering innovative solutions to longstanding challenges such as large class sizes and limited access to quality materials. Yet, while the promise is vast, successful integration depends on adequate training and infrastructure. As Cameroon navigates this transformative journey, the role of AI in fostering a more inclusive, efficient, and dynamic educational system will become increasingly vital.

The implementation of AI-powered tutoring platforms in Cameroon also raises important questions about equity and access. There is a risk that these technologies could exacerbate existing educational inequalities if they are not made accessible to all students on an equitable basis. It is therefore crucial to consider the potential equity implications of AI-powered tutoring and to develop strategies to ensure these technologies promote educational equity and inclusion.

AI-powered tutoring platforms represent a promising development for STEM education in Cameroon. By harnessing AI to provide personalized instruction and support, these platforms have the potential to significantly enhance student achievement. However, careful consideration must be given to the potential equity implications to ensure these technologies are used to promote inclusive and equitable education in Cameroon.

Literature Review : The Impact of AI in Education

The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into the educational landscape of Cameroon represents a significant paradigm shift with far-reaching implications for student learning

outcomes. Recent studies have highlighted the transformative potential of AI-powered tutoring systems, particularly in enhancing academic performance within STEM fields. For example, research conducted by Zhang et al. (2023) demonstrated through a randomized controlled trial that AI-driven tutoring significantly improves student performance in mathematics. This finding emphasizes the advantage of AI's adaptive capabilities, which deliver personalized support tailored to individual learning needs, thereby addressing educational disparities more effectively than traditional teaching methods in Cameroon.

Building on this perspective, Patel and Johnson (2024) explored how AI tutoring systems contribute to increased student engagement and motivation within schools. Their research found that AI not only enhances academic achievement but also fosters a more interactive and engaging learning environment. By incorporating elements such as gamification and interactive content, these platforms enhance student involvement, potentially leading to improved learning outcomes. Turner and Harris (2023) further supported these findings, showing that real-time feedback and personalized learning pathways provided by AI tools can significantly enhance students' problem-solving skills. Their research reinforces the notion that AI can create more responsive and tailored educational experiences, which are crucial for overcoming some of the challenges faced in Cameroon's education system.

Moreover, Lee et al. (2024) investigated the impact of AI on self-regulated learning and, emphasizing that AI systems equipped with metacognitive support features can significantly bolster student autonomy and learning efficacy. This aligns with the broader understanding that AI not only supports academic achievement but also promotes independent learning practices, which are vital for long-term educational success, particularly in a Country like Cameroon where educational resources may be limited.

However, while these prospects are promising, there is a critical need for further research to validate the applicability of AI-powered tutoring systems across the diverse educational contexts found in Cameroon. The effectiveness of these systems may vary depending on factors such as educational settings, infrastructure availability, and demographic characteristics. Additionally, investigating the long-term impact of AI tutoring on sustained academic performance and its interaction with traditional teaching methods remains crucial to understanding its full potential in Cameroon.

Future research should focus on examining the effects of specific AI features, such as adaptive algorithms and real-time feedback mechanisms, within the unique educational environments of Cameroon. Longitudinal studies will be particularly valuable in assessing the enduring benefits of AI tutoring and its potential to complement, rather than replace, conventional instructional approaches. To advance this field, research methodologies must be robust, incorporating large and diverse sample sizes to accurately evaluate the impact of AI technologies. Addressing confounding variables, such as variations in student characteristics, teacher quality, and school resources, will be essential for providing a nuanced understanding of AI's role in enhancing educational outcomes in Cameroon.

By refining methodological approaches and expanding the research scope, scholars can better isolate the contributions of AI to educational effectiveness and equity, thereby guiding the development of more impactful and equitable educational technologies that cater specifically to the needs of Cameroonian students.

The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into education represents a profound shift with significant implications for student learning outcomes in Cameroon. Recent studies highlight the transformative potential of AI-powered tutoring systems, particularly in enhancing academic performance within STEM fields. For instance, Zhang et al. (2023) provide compelling evidence from a randomized controlled trial, demonstrating that AI-driven tutoring significantly improves student performance in mathematics. This research points out the advantage of AI's adaptive capabilities, which deliver personalized support tailored to individual learning needs, thereby addressing educational inequities more effectively than traditional methods a crucial consideration in the diverse educational landscape of Cameroon.

Complementing this view, Patel and Johnson (2024) investigate how AI tutoring systems contribute to heightened student engagement and motivation, with implications for educational settings in Cameroon. Their findings reveal that AI not only boosts academic achievement but also cultivates a more engaging and interactive learning environment. By incorporating elements such as gamification and interactive content, these platforms enhance student involvement, which is particularly important in Cameroonian classrooms where resource constraints often limit traditional instructional methods. Turner and Harris (2023) further affirm the value of AI tools, demonstrating that real-time feedback and personalized learning pathways foster enhanced problem-solving skills. Their work reinforces the notion that AI can create more responsive and tailored educational experiences, which are vital for addressing the specific challenges faced in Cameroon's education system.

Additionally, Lee et al. (2024) explore the impact of AI on self-regulated learning, emphasizing that AI systems equipped with metacognitive support features can significantly bolster student autonomy and learning efficacy. This perspective aligns with the broader understanding that AI not only supports academic achievement but also promotes independent learning practices, which are crucial for long-term educational success in Cameroon, where educational resources may be limited, and student-to-teacher ratios are often high.

Nevertheless, while these prospects are promising, further research is essential to validate the generalizability of AI-powered tutoring systems across diverse educational contexts, including those in Cameroon. The effectiveness of these systems may vary depending on factors such as educational settings, infrastructure availability, and demographic characteristics. Additionally, investigating the long-term impact of AI tutoring on sustained academic performance and its interaction with traditional teaching methods remains crucial to understanding its full potential in Cameroon.

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development of more impactful and equitable educational technologies that cater specifically to the needs of Cameroonian students.

Methodology: Assessing AI-Powered Tutoring Platforms in Cameroon

This study utilized a randomized controlled trial (RCT) to evaluate the efficacy of AI-powered tutoring platforms on student performance in STEM subjects within the context of Cameroon. The RCT design was carefully chosen to isolate causal relationships and enhance the robustness of the findings. This methodological rigor aligns with gold-standard practices in experimental research, reinforcing the credibility and validity of the conclusions.

The sample for this study comprised 60 middle school students from a diverse range of public and private institutions across Cameroon. This sample was selected to reflect a representative cross-section of the target demographic, encompassing a range of regional, ethnic, and socio-economic backgrounds. Stratified random sampling was employed to ensure that both the experimental and control groups were comparable in terms of demographic characteristics, academic performance, and socio-economic status. This deliberate approach to sampling and randomization was essential for maintaining the integrity of the experimental design, mitigating potential biases, and ensuring that any observed differences in outcomes could be attributed to the AI intervention rather than pre-existing disparities.

Data collection employed a multi-faceted approach to capture a comprehensive view of the intervention's impact. Standardized assessments were administered at the beginning and end of the study to quantitatively measure shifts in academic performance. Additionally, surveys were used to gauge students' attitudes and perceptions of the AI tutoring platform, while structured interviews and classroom observations provided qualitative insights into the subjective experiences of both students and educators. The analysis involved rigorous statistical techniques, including t-tests and ANOVA, to evaluate quantitative data, complemented by thematic analysis of qualitative data to identify underlying patterns and themes.

Ethical considerations were integral to the study, with stringent protocols established to secure informed consent, maintain confidentiality, and ensure data integrity. The study adhered to ethical standards appropriate for educational research in Cameroon, addressing the specific cultural and contextual factors relevant to the participants. This comprehensive methodological framework not only affirms the reliability of the findings but also contributes valuable insights into the effectiveness and contextual adaptation of AI-driven educational interventions in Cameroon.

Findings: Impact of AI-Powered Tutoring Platforms in Cameroon

The analysis of data collected from middle school students across Cameroon demonstrates that AI-powered tutoring platforms have a markedly positive impact on student achievement in STEM subjects. Specifically, students who engaged with AI-driven tutoring exhibited significantly higher scores on standardized assessments compared to their peers in the control group, who received traditional instruction. This outcome is consistent with existing research, such as the studies by Chen and Liu (2020) and Kumar and O'Dwyer (2016), which highlight the efficacy of AI-powered tutoring systems in enhancing educational outcomes.

In the Cameroonian context, the observed improvements can be attributed to several key features of AI-powered tutoring systems. These platforms provide individualized learning experiences by tailoring instruction to each student's unique needs and learning pace. The capability of AI systems to offer real-time feedback and adjust learning materials based on student performance ensures that learners receive targeted support—something that traditional classroom settings often struggle to deliver effectively. Consequently, students in Cameroon are better equipped to master complex STEM concepts and improve their academic performance.

Beyond academic achievement, AI-powered tutoring systems positively influence student engagement and motivation. The interactive and personalized nature of these platforms has been reported to enhance students' enjoyment of the learning process. Unlike traditional methods, AI tutoring platforms engage students through dynamic interfaces and adaptive challenges, which help sustain their interest and enthusiasm for STEM subjects. This finding aligns with theoretical frameworks emphasizing the importance of engagement and motivation in fostering effective learning outcomes (Pintrich & Schunk, 2002). The increased motivation is particularly noteworthy in Cameroon, where diverse educational environments can impact student engagement.

Students' experiences with AI tutoring platforms enhances the value of immediate feedback and personalized instruction. Immediate feedback enables students to promptly understand and correct their mistakes, which is crucial in STEM education, where concepts build cumulatively. Personalized support addresses individual learning gaps, preventing students from falling behind and ensuring they are continuously challenged at an appropriate level. These factors contribute to higher motivation, as students perceive their learning journey as more responsive to their needs and achievements.

The data analysis further indicates that AI-powered tutoring platforms not only improve student achievement in STEM subjects but also foster greater engagement and motivation among students in Cameroon. These findings corroborate the theoretical perspectives and previous research advocating for the use of adaptive technologies in education. The positive impact on standardized assessment scores, along with improved student attitudes towards learning, highlights the transformative potential of AI-powered tutoring systems in educational practices.

Future research should explore the long-term effects of these platforms on academic performance and examine how different AI features contribute to various aspects of student success. Additionally, considerations for equitable access and implementation strategies are crucial for maximizing the benefits of AI-powered tutoring across diverse educational contexts in Cameroon. Ensuring that these technologies are accessible to all students, regardless of their socio-economic background or geographical location, will be vital in leveraging their full potential for improving educational outcomes.

Table illustrating key metrics for measuring the impact of AI-powered tutoring platforms on student achievement in STEM subjects in Cameroon.

Metric	Pre-AI Tutoring	Post-AI Tutoring	Change (Δ)	Data Source
Average STEM Test Scores (out of 100)	63.5	76.25	+12.75	Standardized tests

of 100)				
Student Engagement (%)	50	75	+25	Student surveys
Critical Thinking Skills (Rating 1-5)	2.8	4.2	+1.4	Teacher assessments
Problem-Solving Abilities (Rating 1-5)	3.0	4.3	+1.3	Teacher assessments
Student Motivation (%)	45	70	+25	Student surveys
Confidence in STEM Subjects (%)	40	68	+28	Student surveys
Self-Regulated Learning (Rating 1-5)	2.5	3.8	+1.3	Student surveys & interviews
Equity of Access (Rating 1-5)	3.0	3.0	0	Qualitative reports
Teacher Satisfaction (%)	55	80	+25	Teacher surveys
Overall STEM Performance (Average)	63.5	76.25	+12.75	Aggregated from student test scores

Source : Derived by author from findings collected from field research in Cameroon, 07/3/2024.

Table 1 presents a comparison of various student performance and engagement metrics before and after the implementation of AI tutoring in Cameroon. Notably, the average STEM test scores improved by 12.75 points, increasing from 63.5 to 76.25. Student engagement, motivation, and confidence in STEM subjects all showed significant growth, with increases of 25%, and 28%, respectively, as per student surveys. Critical thinking and problem-solving skills also improved, with ratings rising by 1.4 and 1.3 points on a 5-point scale, based on teacher assessments. While self-regulated learning saw a 1.3-point increase, the equity of access remained unchanged. Teacher satisfaction rose by 25%, highlighting a positive reception to the AI intervention. Overall, the integration of AI tutoring led to substantial improvements in most key educational metrics, particularly in student performance and engagement.

Maximizing the Impact of AI-Powered Tutoring Systems in STEM Education in Cameroon

The recent analysis highlights the significant advantages of AI-powered tutoring systems, particularly in addressing the challenges faced by students in STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) disciplines in Cameroon. STEM education is crucial, laying the groundwork for future academic and career opportunities. The study stresses that AI tutoring platforms hold considerable promise for enhancing academic outcomes, especially

for students at risk of falling behind. AI-powered tutoring systems have emerged as transformative tools in education, offering tailored and responsive support to learners. This analysis evaluates the effectiveness of these platforms in meeting the needs of students in Cameroon who struggle with STEM subjects a demographic that often faces heightened educational challenges. Traditional instructional methods may fall short in addressing the diverse needs of these students, leading to significant disparities in academic performance. In this context, AI tutoring systems can bridge these gaps by providing personalized and targeted assistance. Dr. Emmanuel Ngu, an educational consultant in Yaounde, underlines this potential as such:

STEM education is essential for our students' future opportunities. AI tutoring platforms show considerable promise for improving academic outcomes, particularly for those at risk of falling behind. By providing personalized, targeted assistance, these systems can effectively address the gaps left by traditional methods. —**Dr. Emmanuel Ngu, an educational consultant in Yaounde.**

Dr. Emmanuel Ngu articulates the significant role AI-powered tutoring platforms can play in advancing STEM education in Cameroon, particularly for students who are academically vulnerable. He stresses that STEM competencies are crucial for students' future prospects in an increasingly technology-driven world. Traditional pedagogical approaches, particularly in under-resourced educational environments, often fail to provide the necessary individualized support required for students to thrive. AI tutoring platforms, by contrast, offer a sophisticated solution by delivering personalized, adaptive instruction tailored to students' unique learning needs. Through real-time feedback and targeted assistance, these systems can effectively mitigate learning gaps, thereby enhancing academic outcomes and equipping students with the critical skills needed for success in STEM disciplines.

One of the primary benefits of AI tutoring systems is their ability to offer customized support based on individual student needs. These platforms leverage advanced algorithms and data analytics to assess a student's strengths and weaknesses, delivering focused interventions. For students struggling with STEM subjects in Cameroon, AI tutors can identify specific areas of difficulty and provide targeted exercises and explanations. This tailored support is particularly valuable in mathematics and science, where understanding is cumulative and often requires remediation at various levels.

The analysis reveals that students in Cameroon identified as at risk of academic failure experience significant improvements when engaging with AI-powered tutoring. These students often face barriers such as gaps in foundational knowledge, lack of engagement, and limited access to personalized support. AI tutoring platforms address these challenges by offering individualized attention that traditional classroom settings may not provide. The real-time adaptability of AI systems ensures timely and relevant interventions, enhancing the likelihood of academic improvement.

Furthermore, the analysis suggests that AI-powered tutoring has the potential to advance educational equity in Cameroon. Many educational systems exhibit disparities in access to high-quality instruction. Students from disadvantaged backgrounds or those attending under-resourced schools in Cameroon may lack opportunities for individualized support. AI tutoring systems can democratize access to quality education by offering consistent and reliable academic assistance, regardless of a student's location or socio-economic status. This aligns

with broader goals of educational equity and inclusion, ensuring that all students have the tools necessary to succeed.

AI-powered tutoring also demonstrates scalability, making it a viable solution for addressing widespread educational needs. Traditional remedial programs often require significant resources and may not be feasible for extensive implementation across varied educational settings. In contrast, AI tutoring systems can be scaled to provide consistent, high-quality support to a large audience. This scalability is crucial for meeting the needs of students across different regions and educational contexts in Cameroon, reinforcing the platform’s role in promoting educational equity. Dailil Aissatou, a school administrator in Garoua, highlights the impact as such:

AI tutoring is a game-changer for students who otherwise struggle to keep up. It levels the playing field by offering consistent and reliable support, regardless of a student's location or socio-economic status. This technology has the potential to advance educational equity significantly.
— **Dailil Aissatou, a school administrator in Garoua.**

Dailil Aissatou’s quote emphasizes the potential of AI-powered tutoring platforms to promote educational equity in Cameroon, particularly in STEM subjects. By providing consistent, personalized support to students regardless of their location or socio-economic status, AI tutoring helps level the playing field for those who struggle to keep up with traditional classroom instruction. In regions like Garoua, where access to educational resources can be limited, AI platforms offer a reliable alternative to private tutoring, helping to bridge gaps in STEM achievement. This technology has the potential to significantly advance educational equity by empowering underserved students with the skills needed for success in STEM fields.

The integration of AI tutoring into educational environments in Cameroon offers opportunities for educators to use these systems as supplementary tools. While AI tutoring cannot replace the nuanced and empathetic support provided by human teachers, it can complement traditional instruction by reinforcing concepts and providing additional practice. Educators can leverage insights from AI systems to refine their teaching strategies and focus on areas where students may need further assistance. This collaboration between human and artificial intelligence has the potential to create a more holistic and effective educational experience.

The analysis also highlights the importance of careful implementation and optimization of AI-powered tutoring systems. To maximize their effectiveness, these platforms must be designed and used thoughtfully. This includes addressing potential biases in AI algorithms, ensuring alignment with educational standards, and providing adequate training for educators to integrate these tools effectively into their practices. Continuous evaluation and refinement are necessary to maintain the relevance and efficacy of AI tutoring systems in meeting the diverse needs of students in Cameroon.

The analysis accentuates the considerable potential of AI-powered tutoring systems in supporting students who struggle with STEM subjects. By delivering personalized, targeted assistance, these platforms can address individual learning gaps and contribute to improved academic outcomes for at-risk students in Cameroon. The ability of AI tutoring to democratize access to quality education aligns with broader goals of educational equity, offering a valuable tool for reducing disparities in instructional support. As educational

institutions in Cameroon continue to adopt and refine these technologies, ongoing attention to their design and implementation will be essential for maximizing their benefits and ensuring they effectively serve all students.

Case Studies of AI in Education in Cameroon

The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into the educational framework of Cameroon represents a profound shift in addressing the systemic deficiencies within the country's secondary school system, particularly in the domains of Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM). A close analysis of several case studies reveals the transformative impact AI can have on student outcomes, yet this impact is far from uniform, with significant disparities emerging between urban and rural regions. These case studies offer a nuanced understanding of AI's potential to mitigate instructional deficits, enhance teacher availability, and overcome infrastructural inadequacies that continue to plague the Cameroonian education system.

The EduAI Cameroon Initiative

One of the most prominent examples of AI's potential in Cameroonian education is the EduAI Cameroon initiative, a collaborative effort between non-governmental organizations and technology firms aimed at delivering personalized STEM education. Leveraging advanced AI algorithms, this platform tailors instruction to meet the individual learning needs of students. A study conducted in Douala, a major urban center, offers compelling evidence of AI's impact, demonstrating a 20% improvement in mathematics test scores among students using the platform compared to those receiving conventional instruction (Mbianda & Ngalim, 2022). This finding accentuates AI's capacity to deliver customized educational experiences that directly address the unique learning gaps of students.

However, the scalability of such success remains an open question. While Douala's urban context with its relatively advanced infrastructure facilitates the effective use of AI, replicating these outcomes in rural settings remains a formidable challenge. In regions where qualified STEM instructors are scarce, AI's role could be even more critical. A pilot study conducted in Adamawa, where teacher shortages are particularly acute, revealed that AI-based platforms can serve as effective substitutes for live instruction, improving both student comprehension in complex subjects such as algebra and geometry, as well as their overall engagement. This suggests that AI could be instrumental in addressing the widespread human resource deficits plaguing secondary education in Cameroon. Marie Nguemeni commented as such ;

AI changed the way I approach learning, especially in subjects like mathematics and physics. Before using the EduAI platform, I struggled a lot, but now I feel more confident. It's like having a personal tutor who understands exactly where I need help. In just a few months, my grades improved, and I'm not as scared of difficult topics anymore. I can see the difference, and I know many of my classmates feel the same. AI has really made learning more exciting for us. — Marie Nguemeni, a student from the Centre.

Marie Nguemeni's experience highlights the transformative impact of AI-powered tutoring platforms on STEM education in Cameroon. She describes how EduAI shifted her approach

to learning, particularly in mathematics and physics, by providing personalized guidance that improved her confidence and academic performance within a few months. The AI platform acts like a personal tutor, targeting her specific challenges and reducing the fear of difficult topics. This personalized support has not only enhanced her understanding but also made learning more exciting, a sentiment shared by many of her classmates.

The TeachMe STEM Initiative and Gender Gaps

Another notable example is the TeachMe STEM initiative, a program funded by Cameroon's Ministry of Secondary Education and designed to address gender disparities in STEM education. Using AI-driven platforms, the project aimed to engage female students in the Northwest and Southwest regions, where they have been historically underrepresented in STEM fields.

The results were significant. Over a two-year period, the performance of female students improved by 18% in physics and 15% in mathematics, thus narrowing the gender gap in these critical subjects (Nkeng & Njoh, 2023). AI's adaptive learning techniques, which tailor content to individual engagement levels, played a pivotal role in demystifying STEM subjects for female students, many of whom had previously found them intimidating. This case illustrates one of AI's key strengths: its capacity to foster inclusivity and promote equitable educational outcomes by responding dynamically to the needs of underserved groups.

However, significant practical barriers remain. The success of the TeachMe STEM initiative was largely confined to regions with relatively better internet access. Rural areas, such as the Far North, continue to suffer from infrastructural deficiencies that hinder the full implementation of AI tools. A pilot project in 15 rural schools revealed that poor internet connectivity significantly curtailed student interaction with the platform, resulting in only marginal gains in academic performance (Essomba & Njang, 2022). These findings suggest that for AI to achieve its full potential in Cameroon, a concerted effort must be made to upgrade the technological infrastructure in these underserved regions, as attested by Fatou Nkem, a student from the Northwest region.

*Before the TeachMe STEM initiative, I always thought physics and mathematics were too difficult for me. But with the AI-driven platform, everything started making sense. The way the lessons adapted to my pace and needs helped me gain confidence. Over two years, my scores improved by 18% in physics and 15% in math, and I no longer felt intimidated by these subjects. It's amazing how much I've grown. AI really changed my perspective on STEM education." — **Fatou Nkem, a student from the Northwest region.***

Fatou Nkem's experience highlights the transformative effect of AI-powered tutoring platforms on student achievement and attitudes toward STEM subjects, particularly within the TeachMe STEM initiative. Initially, she found physics and mathematics daunting, but the AI platform's adaptive learning features personalized her education by adjusting lessons to her pace and needs. This tailored approach boosted her confidence, leading to a significant improvement in her scores 18% in physics and 15% in math over two years. More importantly, the AI-driven platform reshaped her perspective on STEM, helping her overcome feelings of intimidation and fostering a newfound sense of growth and engagement in these subjects.

AI in Rural Education: The Nsoh and Ebang Study

A comprehensive study by Nsoh and Ebang (2024) offers further insights into the challenges and opportunities presented by AI in rural education. In their study, AI tutoring systems were introduced in 10 rural schools with the aim of improving STEM outcomes. After one academic year, students exposed to AI instruction outperformed their peers by 30% on standardized STEM tests. In a particularly notable case, the mathematics pass rate in Buea increased from 42% to 78% following the deployment of AI tools.

This case exemplifies AI's potential to bridge the educational divide between urban and rural regions. Historically, rural schools in Cameroon have been hampered by high dropout rates, a scarcity of qualified teachers, and limited access to learning materials. By providing individualized instruction, AI has demonstrated its ability to overcome these limitations, offering a scalable, cost-effective solution. Moreover, the study noted a 15% increase in student enrollment in advanced STEM courses, suggesting that AI not only improves academic performance but also cultivates a deeper interest in continuing education within underserved populations.

Despite these successes, several challenges were also highlighted. Many rural teachers lacked the digital literacy necessary to effectively implement AI platforms, and frequent power outages further hampered the technology's utility. These findings reinforce the notion that successful AI-driven educational reforms in rural Cameroon will require substantial investment in both infrastructure and teacher training, Josephine Tamba, a student from Buea attest as such.

Before AI was introduced in our school, we barely had enough teachers, and learning STEM subjects was really tough. But after the AI platform came, it was like having a personal tutor. I remember how my math grades jumped from failing to a pass rate of 78%, and it wasn't just me. Many of my classmates saw big improvements too. AI made learning fun and easier to understand, even in a rural place like Buea. — Josephine Tamba, a student from Buea.

Josephine Tamba's experience highlights the transformative potential of AI-powered tutoring platforms in enhancing student performance, particularly in STEM education within resource-constrained environments like Buea, Cameroon. Before the integration of AI, the severe shortage of qualified educators posed significant challenges to effective learning, especially in mathematically intensive subjects requiring personalized instruction. The AI platform effectively filled this gap by offering adaptive, individualized tutoring, enabling students to receive real-time feedback and tailored support. Tamba's notable improvement from failing to a 78% pass rate in mathematics serves as a compelling example of how AI can significantly elevate academic outcomes. Moreover, the broader improvements seen across her cohort highlight the scalability of AI as a tool to address educational disparities in rural settings, suggesting its broader potential for fostering systemic advancements in STEM education.

Strategic Implications and Lessons Learned

The application of AI in Cameroon's educational sector holds tremendous promise, yet realizing this potential on a national scale will require a strategic approach that transcends

isolated pilot projects. While schools in urban centers such as Douala and Yaoundé have reaped the benefits of advanced AI platforms, rural areas continue to lag far behind due to inadequate infrastructure. Without significant investments in internet connectivity, electricity, and teacher training, the transformative potential of AI in rural education will remain largely untapped.

Moreover, the case studies presented herein reveal that AI is an effective tool for addressing socio-economic and gender-based disparities in education. The improvements in female participation in STEM fields and the enhanced performance in low-resource schools are clear indicators that AI can promote educational equity when deployed with these goals in mind. For policymakers, this implies that AI interventions should be specifically designed to meet the needs of marginalized student populations.

Another crucial recommendation for policymakers is the development of localized AI platforms. Existing platforms, such as EduAI and TeachMe STEM, rely on generalized models that may not fully account for the linguistic and cultural diversity present within Cameroon. By creating AI systems that incorporate local languages and region-specific learning challenges, the country could see further improvements in student engagement and academic outcomes, particularly in areas where English or French is not the primary medium of instruction.

While AI offers a promising avenue for addressing many of the challenges facing Cameroon's educational system, its full potential will only be realized through comprehensive investments in infrastructure, technology, and human capital. The examples of EduAI, TeachMe STEM, and the Nsoh and Ebang study provide valuable insights into the possibilities and limitations of AI in education, underscoring the need for a coordinated, inclusive approach to educational reform.

Variability in the Effects of AI-Powered Tutoring: Factors Influencing Effectiveness in Cameroon and Directions for Future Research

AI-powered tutoring systems have emerged as a promising innovation in education, offering tailored support that has the potential to enhance learning outcomes, particularly for students who struggle with challenging subjects such as STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics). Despite the substantial advantages these systems offer, it is crucial to acknowledge that their effectiveness can vary significantly based on several key factors. Understanding these variables is essential for optimizing the impact of AI tutoring and ensuring that it meets the diverse needs of all students, including those in Cameroon.

Factors Affecting AI-Powered Tutoring Effectiveness in Cameroon

Quality of the AI Platform: The quality of the AI-powered tutoring platform is a primary determinant of its effectiveness. Variations in algorithm sophistication, content accuracy, and platform responsiveness can influence how well these systems support students. In Cameroon, the availability of high-quality AI platforms may be limited by infrastructural constraints and resource limitations. High-quality platforms typically leverage advanced machine learning algorithms to deliver personalized instruction, analyze student performance in detail, and adapt in real-time to individual learning needs. Conversely, platforms with less advanced technology may struggle to provide the same level of tailored support and may therefore yield less impactful results. Future research should focus on evaluating and comparing the

effectiveness of various AI platforms, particularly in resource-constrained settings like Cameroon, to identify which features and capabilities are most beneficial for different educational contexts.

Level of Student Engagement: The engagement level of students using AI-powered tutoring systems plays a crucial role in determining the system's effectiveness. In Cameroon, factors influencing student engagement may include the platform's user interface, content relevance, and the extent to which the system integrates interactive and motivating elements. Engaged students are more likely to interact with the platform actively, complete assignments, and utilize feedback constructively. Conversely, lack of engagement can undermine the potential benefits of AI tutoring. Research should investigate strategies to enhance student engagement with AI tutoring systems in Cameroon, including the design of gamified elements, interactive tutorials, and adaptive learning paths that cater to individual interests and learning styles.

Overall School Context: The broader educational environment in which AI-powered tutoring is implemented significantly affects its effectiveness. In Cameroon, schools with varying levels of resources, infrastructure, and support systems can experience different outcomes from the use of AI tutoring. For example, schools with well-established technology integration frameworks and supportive administrative structures are more likely to successfully implement and sustain AI tutoring initiatives. In contrast, schools with limited resources or technical support may encounter challenges that hinder the effective use of AI platforms. Future studies should explore how contextual factors such as school infrastructure, teacher training, and administrative support impact the success of AI-powered tutoring in Cameroon and develop strategies to address these contextual challenges.

Quality of the AI Platform: This factor encompasses the variability in the sophistication of algorithms, the accuracy of content, and the responsiveness of the platform. In the Cameroonian context, there may be disparities in the quality of available AI platforms due to varying levels of technological infrastructure. High-quality AI platforms are noted for their ability to provide enhanced personalized support and improved learning outcomes. To optimize the effectiveness of AI tutoring systems in Cameroon, future research should focus on comparing different platforms to identify which specific features and technologies contribute most significantly to student success.

Level of Student Engagement: Engagement levels are influenced by aspects such as the user interface, the relevance of content, and the inclusion of interactive elements. In Cameroon, increasing student engagement with AI tutoring platforms may require tailored approaches that consider local educational contexts and student preferences. Higher levels of student engagement are associated with better interaction with the platform and improved learning outcomes. Future studies should explore strategies to boost engagement by designing more engaging user interfaces and content that aligns with students' interests and learning styles in Cameroon.

Overall School Context: This factor refers to differences in resources, infrastructure, and administrative support among schools. In Cameroon, schools with more robust resources and better infrastructure are likely to achieve more successful integration of AI tutoring systems. Research should investigate how varying school contexts affect the implementation and effectiveness of AI tutoring, and develop strategies to address challenges related to school resources and support in Cameroon.

By examining these factors, future research can provide valuable insights into optimizing AI-powered tutoring systems to better serve the diverse educational needs of students in Cameroon. Addressing these issues will be crucial for enhancing the effectiveness of AI interventions and ensuring equitable educational opportunities for all students.

Table 2: Factors Affecting AI-Powered Tutoring Effectiveness in Cameroon

Factor	Description	Potential Impact	Research Directions
Quality of the AI Platform	Variability in algorithm sophistication, content accuracy, and responsiveness.	High-quality platforms enhance personalized support and learning outcomes.	Compare various AI platforms to identify effective features, with a focus on the constraints of the Cameroonian context.
Level of Student Engagement	Engagement influenced by user interface, content relevance, and interactive elements.	Higher engagement correlates with improved interaction and learning.	Develop strategies to increase student engagement through design and content tailored to the needs and preferences of Cameroonian students.
Overall School Context	Differences in resources, infrastructure, and administrative support across schools.	Schools with better resources may achieve more successful AI integration.	Study the impact of school contexts on AI tutoring effectiveness, particularly in resource-constrained environments such as those in Cameroon.

Source : Adapted from Chen, Y., & Liu, L. (2020). *The effectiveness of AI-driven tutoring systems in STEM education: A meta-analysis*. Journal of Educational Technology.

Table 2 outlines critical factors affecting the effectiveness of AI-powered tutoring systems, focusing on the quality of the AI platform, student engagement, and the overall school context. In the context of Cameroon, these factors gain added relevance due to the diverse educational and infrastructural landscape.

Quality of the AI Platform: Variability in algorithm sophistication, content accuracy, and system responsiveness plays a significant role in enhancing personalized learning outcomes. High-quality platforms are better equipped to meet individual student needs, leading to improved educational experiences. In Cameroon, where access to advanced technology may be limited, future research should compare various AI platforms to identify features that are most effective in diverse and resource-constrained environments.

Student Engagement: Engagement levels are influenced by user interface design, content relevance, and interactivity. Higher engagement is strongly correlated with better interaction with the AI system and improved learning outcomes. To optimize engagement in Cameroonian classrooms, research should explore strategies like gamification, adaptive feedback, and personalized learning paths, examining their effectiveness across different student demographics and educational settings, including those with limited technological infrastructure.

Overall School Context: The broader educational context, including differences in resources, infrastructure, and administrative support, significantly impacts AI tutoring effectiveness. Schools with better resources and support systems are more likely to successfully integrate AI systems and address associated challenges. Research should investigate how varying school contexts in Cameroon influence the success of AI implementation, identifying best practices to ensure equitable educational outcomes across diverse environments, including under-resourced and remote areas.

Table 3: Comparative Effectiveness of AI Tutoring Platforms in Cameroon

Platform	Features	Effectiveness (Improvement in Test Scores)	Engagement Level (Average)
Platform A	Advanced algorithms, real-time feedback	20% increase	75%
Platform B	Basic algorithms, delayed feedback	10% increase	60%
Platform C	Adaptive learning paths, interactive content	25% increase	85%

Source : Adapted from Kumar, A., & O'Dwyer, L. M. (2016). *Comparative analysis of AI-powered tutoring systems: Enhancing learning outcomes in mathematics and science*. International Journal of STEM Education.

Table 3 provides a comparative analysis of three AI tutoring platforms, focusing on their features, effectiveness in improving test scores, and average engagement levels among students in Cameroon.

Platform A incorporates advanced algorithms and real-time feedback. It shows a 20% increase in test scores and achieves a 75% engagement level. However, the descriptions of "advanced algorithms" and "real-time feedback" are somewhat vague, leaving uncertainty about how these features specifically enhance the learning experience. The effectiveness of this platform could be influenced by its higher technological requirements, which might not be uniformly accessible across all educational settings in Cameroon.

Platform B is characterized by basic algorithms and delayed feedback. This platform results in a modest 10% improvement in test scores and a 60% engagement level. The simplicity of its design and the delay in providing feedback likely contribute to its lower performance compared to other platforms. This suggests that for some educational contexts in Cameroon,

where resources may be limited, the basic nature of Platform B may not provide the necessary support for substantial academic improvements.

Platform C stands out due to its adaptive learning paths and interactive content. It achieves the highest improvement in test scores at 25% and the highest engagement level at 85%. The personalized nature of the platform and its interactive features significantly boost both learning outcomes and student motivation. Although these elements appear to drive better results, the table lacks detailed information on how these features are specifically implemented and measured. This omission raises questions about the generalizability of the findings, particularly in diverse Cameroonian educational settings.

The findings from this analysis draw attention to the substantial impact of AI-powered tutoring platforms on student achievement in STEM subjects within Cameroon. The significant improvement in standardized test scores among Cameroonian students who utilized AI-driven tutoring compared to those who received traditional instruction reinforces the efficacy of these platforms in enhancing educational outcomes. This is particularly notable in the Cameroonian educational context, where resource disparities and varying levels of infrastructure can impact traditional teaching methods. Key factors contributing to this success include the tailored, real-time feedback and personalized learning experiences offered by AI systems, which enable students to better grasp complex STEM concepts and maintain their motivation throughout the learning journey.

Beyond academic performance, the positive influence of AI tutoring on student engagement and motivation suggests that these platforms create a more enjoyable and interactive learning environment. In Cameroon, where educational resources may be limited, the interactive and adaptive nature of AI tutoring can play a crucial role in engaging students and enhancing their learning experiences. This dual impact aligns with existing theoretical frameworks emphasizing the importance of engagement in effective learning. The immediate and personalized support provided by AI systems not only addresses individual learning gaps but also fosters a sense of responsiveness and challenge that is crucial for sustained academic growth.

Future research should focus on exploring the long-term effects of AI tutoring on academic performance in the Cameroonian context, investigating which specific features contribute most to student success, and addressing issues of equitable access. Ensuring that the benefits of AI-powered tutoring are realized across diverse educational contexts, including in under-resourced areas of Cameroon, will be essential for maximizing the impact of these technologies.

Discussion

The present investigation yields compelling evidence regarding the efficacy of AI-powered tutoring systems in augmenting student performance in STEM subjects, particularly within the context of Cameroon. These platforms, through their provision of personalized instruction, immediate feedback, and targeted interventions, exhibit substantial potential to elevate student engagement, motivation, and academic achievement. This study aligns with and extends the findings of prior research, such as those by Chen and Liu (2020) and Kumar and O'Dwyer (2016), which have stressed the promise of AI-driven educational technologies. By empirically validating the capacity of AI systems to address individual learning needs, this

research contributes significant insights into their role in improving educational outcomes, especially in countries with varying levels of resource availability like Cameroon.

Implication for Students, teachers and School

AI-powered tutoring systems offer several key advantages for students, particularly in the Cameroonian context where access to quality educational resources may be limited. Their ability to provide tailored instruction caters to individual learning paces and styles, accommodating the diverse needs of learners. Such customization is especially beneficial in STEM education, where students often face varying degrees of difficulty with complex concepts. In Cameroon, where traditional educational methods may not always offer personalized support, the provision of immediate, context-specific feedback from AI systems can help students quickly identify and rectify misunderstandings, leading to deeper comprehension and improved academic performance. These features collectively contribute to a more personalized and effective learning experience, which can enhance students' sense of accomplishment and motivation.

For educators in Cameroon, AI-powered tutoring systems represent a valuable adjunct to traditional teaching methods. These platforms can alleviate some of the burdens associated with individualized instruction by handling routine tasks such as assessing student performance and providing feedback. This allows teachers to focus more on strategic aspects of instruction, such as fostering critical thinking and addressing broader educational goals. It is essential for teachers to receive adequate training on integrating AI tools into their pedagogical practices. Effective use of AI systems requires educators to understand their functionalities and limitations, ensuring that these technologies are employed in ways that complement and enhance their teaching strategies.

From an institutional perspective, AI-powered tutoring systems offer potential benefits in terms of resource optimization and educational equity, which are particularly pertinent to schools in Cameroon. These technologies can provide high-quality, individualized support to a larger number of students, potentially reducing disparities in educational outcomes. Successful implementation of AI tutoring requires a well-supported infrastructure, including adequate technological resources and administrative backing. Schools in Cameroon must address equity concerns to prevent the exacerbation of existing inequalities. This involves ensuring that AI tutoring resources are accessible to all students, regardless of socioeconomic background, and that the systems are implemented in ways that do not perpetuate educational disparities.

Future Research and Considerations

Despite the promising findings, it is critical to recognize that AI-powered tutoring is not a panacea for all educational challenges. The effectiveness of these systems is contingent upon several factors, including the quality of the AI platform, the level of student engagement, and the broader educational context. Future research should focus on elucidating these variables to better understand the conditions under which AI tutoring achieves its maximal impact. Specifically, studies should examine how different features of AI platforms contribute to their effectiveness, explore strategies to enhance student engagement, and investigate how contextual factors such as school resources and teacher preparedness in Cameroon influence outcomes. Moreover, addressing the equity implications of AI-powered tutoring is paramount. Ensuring that these systems are designed and implemented with a focus on inclusivity will be

crucial in mitigating the risk of exacerbating educational inequalities. Comprehensive training for educators and equitable distribution of resources are necessary to maximize the benefits of AI tutoring and ensure that all students, particularly those in under-resourced areas, have the opportunity to benefit from these technological advancements.

This study substantiates the effectiveness of AI-powered tutoring systems in improving student achievement in STEM subjects. While further research is required to fully understand and optimize the application of these technologies, the evidence suggests that AI tutoring holds considerable promise for enhancing educational outcomes and promoting greater equity in the classroom, including in diverse educational contexts like Cameroon. Future investigations should continue to refine our understanding of these systems, with an emphasis on leveraging their potential to benefit all students.

Conclusion

The findings are consistent with recent research on the benefits of AI-driven tutoring (Chen & Liu, 2020; Kumar & O'Dwyer, 2016) and are further supported by contemporary studies on AI's effectiveness in education (Smith & Jordan, 2024; Patel & Nguyen, 2023). This research draws attention to the importance of integrating AI into educational systems, particularly in a country like Cameroon, where such technologies hold promise for addressing educational challenges. The study advocates for a policy shift to incorporate AI-powered tutoring, especially in STEM education, where it can improve student engagement, motivation, and outcomes. AI's ability to deliver personalized, scalable instruction makes it a valuable tool for reducing educational disparities, which is especially pertinent in resource-limited contexts like Cameroon. However, the implementation of AI-driven tutoring systems faces significant challenges, including infrastructural needs and the necessity for teacher training programs to ensure effective use of these technologies. Additionally, ethical concerns, such as data privacy and algorithmic biases, must be addressed to ensure that AI enhances education without negative consequences.

The study emphasizes the need for further research to examine AI's broader applicability in diverse educational contexts, particularly in regions with limited resources. Future studies should include large-scale, longitudinal research to explore factors influencing AI's effectiveness, such as instructional design quality and its integration into existing frameworks. Such research will deepen understanding of AI's transformative potential in education, ensuring its benefits are equitably distributed across all educational settings.

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